

Chloromethylation and Other Studies on Some Benzophenone Derivatives

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2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone did not give a pure product on chloromethylation but its dimethyl ether gave the 5-chloromethyl derivative. Similarly, 2,2'-dimethoxybenzophenone gave the 5,5'-di(chloromethyl) derivative. The chloromethyl derivatives have been converted into the acetoxymethyl derivatives and into the Mannich bases. They have been oxidised to the corresponding carboxylic acids and also converted into the corresponding formyl derivatives by heating with hexamine. 2,4'-Dimethoxy-5'-benzoylflavone, 7,2',4'-trimethoxy-5'-benzoylflavone, bi(4'-methoxy-3'-flavonyl) ketone and bi(7,4'-dimethoxy-3'-flavonyl) ketone have been synthesised from these formyl derivatives through the intermediate chalcone derivatives. The Fries migration of 2,2'-diacetoxymethylbenzophenone and the Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenone gave the 5,5'-diacetyl derivative as the main product.

In continuation of the work described in earlier papers^{1,2} 2,4-dihydroxy- and 2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenone and their dimethyl ethers have now been subjected to various reactions.

2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone on chloromethylation with paraformaldehyde and hydrogen chloride in glacial acetic acid gave a mixture of products from which no pure compound could be isolated. Its dimethyl ether, however, with paraformaldehyde and hydrogen chloride in glacial acetic acid gave the 5-chloromethyl derivative. On alkaline potassium permanganate oxidation it gave 2,4-dimethoxybenzophenone-5-carboxylic acid identical with the one obtained on alkaline hydrolysis of methyl-2,4-dimethoxybenzophenone-5-carboxylate which in turn was synthesised by methylation of methyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone 5-carboxylate, prepared according to Desai and Radha³. Further chloromethylation of the 5-chloromethyl derivative did not give any pure product.

2,4-Dimethoxy-5-chloromethylbenzophenone on heating with hexamine and glacial acetic acid gave the 5-formyl derivative which on reaction with 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine gave a mono 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative.

2,2'-Dimethoxybenzophenone on chloromethylation gave the 5,5'-di(chloromethyl) derivative. Its structure was proved by converting it into 2,2'-dimethoxybenzophenone-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid, identical with the acid obtained on alkaline potassium permanganate oxidation of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-diformyl diphenylmethane synthesised by the condensation of two molecules of anisaldehyde with formaldehyde in the presence of anhydrous zinc chloride.

1. R. A. Balani and S. Sethna, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 52.
2. R. A. Balani and S. Sethna, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 390.
3. R. D. Desai and K. S. Radha, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1940, **12A**, 46.

The 5,5'-di(chloromethyl) derivative on Sommelet reaction gave the 5,5'-diformyl derivative which gave the di-2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative.

The chloromethyl derivatives have also been converted into the corresponding acetoxy-methyl derivatives by reaction with sodium acetate and acetic acid and into Mannich bases by reaction with various amines.

2,4-Dimethoxy-5-formylbenzophenone on condensation with 2-hydroxyacetophenone in the presence of alkaline potassium hydroxide gave 2,4-dimethoxy-5-benzoyl-2'-hydroxy-chalkone. It gave a reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and a red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid. On acetylation with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride it gave an acetoxy derivative. On heating with selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol it gave 2',4'-dimethoxy-5'-benzoylflavone.

Similarly, 7,2',4'-trimethoxy-5'-benzoylflavone was prepared by the condensation of 2,4-dimethoxy-5-formyl benzophenone with 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone in the presence of alcoholic potash to 2,4,4'-trimethoxy-5-benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkone and subjecting this to the action of selenium dioxide.

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-diformylbenzophenone on condensation with 2-hydroxyacetophenone in the presence of alcoholic potash gave bi(2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-chalkonyl) ketone. It gave a reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and a red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid. The bichalkonyl ketone on refluxing with selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol afforded bi(4'-methoxy-3'-flavonyl) ketone. 2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-diformylbenzophenone on a similar condensation with 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone in the presence of alcoholic potash gave bi(2'-hydroxy-4,4'-dimethoxy-3-chalkonyl) ketone which on heating with selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol gave bi-(7-4'-dimethoxy-3'-flavonyl) ketone.

For the synthesis of bi(8-flavonyl) ketone, 2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetylbenzophenone was required. The Fries migration of 2,2'-diacetoxybenzophenone and the Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenone were therefore studied.

2,2'-Diacetoxybenzophenone on Fries migration with anhydrous aluminium chloride at 140° gave a mixture of two products to one of which was assigned 2,2'-dihydroxy-5,5'-diacetylbenzophenone structure as on alkaline potassium permanganate oxidation of its dimethyl ether 2,2'-dimethoxy benzophenone-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid described earlier was obtained. The other isomeric compound was obtained in poor yield and hence could not be studied.

Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenone with either acetyl chloride or acetic anhydride in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene at 140° also afforded the 5,5'-diacetyl derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL*

2,4-Dimethoxy-5-chloromethylbenzophenone : Through a clear solution of 2,4-dimethoxybenzophenone (2.5 g.) and paraformaldehyde (1.0 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml.) dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed for 1½ hr. at room temperature. The product which separated

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

as crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in fine white needles (1.5 g.), m.p. 153–54°. (Found : C, 65.88; H, 5.44; Cl, 12.20%. $C_{16}H_{15}O_3Cl$ requires C, 66.10; H, 5.10; Cl, 12.22%).

The acetoxymethyl derivative : Prepared by refluxing the above chloromethyl derivative with fused sodium acetate and glacial acetic acid for 1 hr. was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 146°. (Found : C, 68.62; H, 5.74. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 68.80; H, 5.30%).

2,4-Dimethoxy-5-dimethylaminomethylbenzophenone : A mixture of 2,4-dimethoxy-5-chloromethylbenzophenone (1.0 g.) and dimethylamine (3 ml. 37% aqueous solution) was heated on a steam bath for 4 hr. and then treated with dilute hydrochloric acid. The product obtained was neutralised with sodium bicarbonate solution. The oily mass obtained on extraction with ether crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 77–78°. (Found : N, 4.50%. $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N$ requires N, 4.68%).

2,4-Dimethoxy-5-piperidinomethylbenzophenone : Obtained from the chloromethyl derivative (1.0 g.) and piperidine (2 ml.) and crystallised from alcohol gave m.p. 141°. (Found : N, 4.19. $C_{21}H_{25}O_3N$ requires N, 4.13%).

5-morpholinomethyl derivative : Prepared from the chloromethyl derivative (1.0 g.) and morpholine (2.0 ml.) as above and crystallised from alcohol gave m.p. 153°. (Found : N, 3.94; $C_{20}H_{23}O_4N$ requires N, 4.10%).

2,4-Dimethoxy-5-formylbenzophenone : 2,4-Dimethoxy-5-chloromethylbenzophenone (2.0 g.) was heated with hexamine (3.0 g.) and glacial acetic acid (15 ml.) on a steam bath for 2 hr. Hydrochloric acid (25 ml.; 1 : 4) was then added and heating continued for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. more. The product separating on cooling was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 125°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 71.46; H, 5.39. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 71.11; H, 5.18%).

The mono-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone : Prepared as usual and crystallised from acetic acid gave m.p. 248–49° (decomp.) (Found : N, 12.67. $C_{22}H_{18}O_7N_4$ requires N, 12.45%).

2,4-Dimethoxybenzophenone-5-carboxylic acid : The above chloromethyl derivative (1.0 g.) was heated on a steam bath with potassium permanganate (1.0 g.) and potassium hydroxide solution (20 ml.; 5%) for 4 hr. More of potassium permanganate (0.5 g.) was added. The excess of potassium permanganate was destroyed with sodium bisulphite and the solution was filtered and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The product obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 188–89°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found : C, 67.23; H, 4.85. $C_{16}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 67.13; H, 4.89%).

The same acid was also obtained when methyl-2,4-dimethoxybenzophenone-5-carboxylate (1.0 g.) (described below) was heated on a steam bath with alcoholic sodium hydroxide (10%) till a clear solution was obtained. The product obtained on acidification, crystallised from dilute alcohol. Mixed m.p. with the above acid was not depressed.

Methyl-2,4-dimethoxybenzophenone-5-carboxylate : Methyl 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone 5-carboxylate (1.0 g.), prepared as reported by Desai and Radha³, was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate (1.5 g.), potassium carbonate (5.0 g.) and dry acetone (20 ml.) for 4 hr. The product obtained on working up as usual was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 158°. Yield 1.0 g. (Found : C, 67.98; H, 5.70. $C_{17}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 68.00; H, 5.34%).

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-di(chloromethyl) benzophenone : Through a clear mixture of 2,2'-dimethoxybenzophenone (4 g.), paraformaldehyde (2.4 g.) and acetic acid (30 ml.), dry hydrogen chloride was passed at 60° for 2 hr. The separated product was crystallised from benzenepetroleum ether mixture, m.p. 140–41°. Yield 3.1 g. (Found : C, 60.23; H, 4.56; Cl, 20.64. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3Cl_2$ requires C, 60.17; H, 4.72; Cl, 20.94%).

The diacetoxymethyl derivative : The above di(chloromethyl) derivative was refluxed with fused sodium acetate and acetic acid for 1 hr. Product which separated on dilution with water crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 132° (Found : C, 65.05; H, 5.79. $C_{21}H_{22}O_7$ requires C, 65.28; H, 5.70%).

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-diformylbenzophenone : The above 5,5'-di(chloromethyl) derivative (2.0 g.) was heated with a mixture of hexamine (6 g.) and acetic acid (15 ml.) on a steam bath for 3 hr. Dilute hydrochloric acid (25 ml.; 1 : 1) was added to the reaction mixture and heating continued for 1 hr. more. It was then diluted with water and the product (0.5 g.) which separated was crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 140°. (Found : C, 68.91; H, 4.84. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.45; H, 4.77%).

The di-2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative : Prepared as usual and crystallised by dissolving in nitrobenzene and precipitating it with petroleum ether gave m.p. 323–25° (decomp.) (Found : N, 16.99; $C_{29}H_{24}O_4N_8$ requires N, 17.20%).

2,2'-Dimethoxybenzophenone-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid : A mixture of the di(chloromethyl) derivative (2 g.), potassium permanganate (2 g.) and potassium hydroxide solution (5%; 80 ml.) was heated on a steam bath for 10 hr. More of potassium permanganate (2.0 g.) was added and the product (1.2 g.) obtained on acidification of the alkaline solution was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 328–29°. (Found : C, 61.6; H, 4.12. $C_{17}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 61.81; H, 4.24%).

The same acid was also obtained on alkaline potassium permanganate oxidation of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-diacetylbenzophenone and of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-diformyl-diphenylmethane.

Dimethyl-2,2'-dimethoxybenzophenone-5,5'-dicarboxylate : A mixture of the above dicarboxylic acid (0.5 g.), dimethyl sulphate (1 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) and acetone (15 ml.) was refluxed for 8 hr. The product obtained on removal of acetone crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 154–55°. (Found : C, 64.08; H, 4.96. $C_{19}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 63.68; H, 5.06%).

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-diformyldiphenylmethane : Anisaldehyde (2.0 g.) was refluxed with formaldehyde solution (2 ml.; 40%), zinc chloride (1 g.) and alcohol for 3 hr. The oily residue obtained after evaporation of alcohol was washed with sodium bicarbonate and then several times with petroleum ether. It could not be purified further as on vacuum distillation it decomposed. It also could not be crystallised. It was therefore directly oxidised to 2,2'-dimethoxybenzophenone-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid described above.

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-di(dimethylaminomethyl)benzophenone hydrochloride : A mixture of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-di(chloromethyl)benzophenone (0.5 g.) and dimethylamine (3 ml., 37%) was heated on a steam bath for 4 hr. It was then treated with dilute hydrochloric acid.

The hydrochloride crystallised from alcohol-ether mixture, m.p. 185–87° (decomp.). (Found : N, 6.38; Cl, 17.08. $C_{21}H_{30}O_3Cl_2N_2$ requires N, 6.52; Cl, 16.55%).

2,4-Dimethoxy-5-benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkone : A mixture of 2,4-dimethoxy-5-formylbenzophenone (1.0 g.), 2-hydroxy-acetophenone (1.0 g.) and potassium hydroxide (3 g. in 3 ml. water) in alcohol (25 ml.) was kept overnight at room temperature. It was then diluted with water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (0.7 g.), m.p. 214–15°. It gave a reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, a red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid and a positive Wilson's boric acid test. (Found : C, 74.25; H, 5.25. $C_{24}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 74.23; H, 5.15%).

The acetoxy derivative : Prepared by refluxing the above chalkone with fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride for 1 hr. was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 166°. (Found : C, 72.23; H, 5.43. $C_{26}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 72.56; H, 5.11%).

2',4'-Dimethoxy-5'-benzoylflavone : A mixture of 2,4-dimethoxy-5-benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkone (1.0 g.) and selenium dioxide (3.0 g.) in isoamyl alcohol (15 ml.) was refluxed in an oil bath at 140–50° for 8 hr. It was filtered hot and the product obtained on cooling the filtrate was crystallised from toluene in fine needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 212°. (Found : C, 74.51; H, 4.51. $C_{24}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 74.61; H, 4.66%). It did not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride or a red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid and was insoluble in alkali.

2,4,4'-Trimethoxy-5-benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkone : Potassium hydroxide (3 g. in 3 ml. water) was added to a mixture of 2,4-dimethoxy-5-formylbenzophenone (1.0 g.) and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone (1.0 g.) in alcohol (25 ml.) and the reaction mixture was kept overnight. The product obtained on dilution with water and acidification was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 227–28°. It gave a reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, a red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid and a positive Wilson's boric acid test. (Found : C, 71.64; H, 5.25. $C_{25}H_{22}O_6$ requires, C, 71.76; H, 5.26%).

The acetoxy derivative : Prepared as usual by refluxing the above chalkone with fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 183°. (Found : C, 70.38; H, 5.24. $C_{27}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 70.42; H, 5.21%).

7,2',4'-Trimethoxy-5'-benzoylflavone : A mixture of the above chalkone (1.0 g.) and selenium dioxide (3.0 g.) in isoamyl alcohol (15 ml.) was refluxed in an oil bath at 140° for 8 hr. It was filtered hot and the product obtained on cooling the filtrate was crystallised from toluene in fine needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 226–27°. (Found : C, 71.61; H, 4.53. $C_{25}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 72.11; H, 4.80%). It did not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride or a red colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid. It was insoluble in alkali.

Bi-(2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-chalkonyl) ketone : To a mixture of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-diformylbenzophenone (1 g.) and 2-hydroxyacetophenone (2 g.) dissolved in sufficient alcohol, potassium hydroxide (6 g. in 6 ml. water) was added and the reaction mixture left overnight. It was then acidified with hydrochloric acid. The precipitated bichalkonyl ketone crystallised from xylene in yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 216°. It gave a faint brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, a red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid and a positive

Wilson's boric acid test. It gave a single spot in TLC. (Found : C, 74.06; H, 4.88. $C_{33}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 74.16; H, 4.53%).

Bi-(4'-methoxy-3'-flavonyl) ketone : The above bichalkonyl ketone derivative (1 g.) was refluxed with isoamyl alcohol (15 ml.) and selenium dioxide (3 g.) in an oil bath at 140° for 6 hr. It was filtered hot and the product which separated on cooling the filtrate crystallised from isoamyl alcohol in white needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 249° . (Found : C, 74.76; H, 4.65. $C_{33}H_{22}O_7$ requires C, 74.71; H, 4.18%).

Bi-(2'-hydroxy-4,4'-dimethoxy-3-chalkonyl) ketone : Potassium hydroxide (5 g. in 6 ml. water) was added to a mixture of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-diformylbenzophenone (1 g.) and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone (2.5 g.) dissolved in alcohol and the reaction mixture was left overnight. The bichalkonyl ketone which separated on acidification crystallised from acetic acid in fine yellow needles (0.5 g.), m.p. $202-03^\circ$. (Found : C, 70.76; H, 4.87. $C_{35}H_{30}O_9$ requires C, 70.69; H, 5.09%). It gave a reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, a red colouration with con. sulphuric acid and a positive Wilson's boric acid test. It gave a single spot in TLC.

Bi-(7,4'-dimethoxy-3'-flavonyl) ketone : The above bichalkonyl ketone (1.0 g.) was refluxed with selenium dioxide (3 g.) in isoamyl alcohol (25 ml.) in an oil bath at 140° for 16 hr. It was filtered hot and the product obtained on cooling the filtrate was crystallised from xylene, m.p. 247° . Yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 70.76; H, 4.02. $C_{35}H_{29}O_9$ requires C, 71.17; H, 4.40%).

2,2'-Dihydroxy-5,5'-diacetylbenzophenone : A mixture of 2,2'-diacetoxybenzophenone (5 g.) and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (10.8 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 140° for 4 hr. It was decomposed with ice cooled hydrochloric acid. The product which separated was purified through sodium hydroxide extraction and then crystallised from benzene in pale yellow needles (2.0 g.), m.p. $178-79^\circ$. (Found : C, 68.29; H, 4.62. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.45; H, 4.7%).

The same compound was also obtained on heating a mixture of 2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenone (2.0 g.), anhydrous aluminium chloride (5 g.) and acetic anhydride (2 g.) or acetyl chloride (3 g.) in nitrobenzene (20 ml.) at 140° for 4 hr. and working up as usual.

The benzene filtrate obtained after removal of 5,5'-diacetyl derivative in the Fries migration of 2,2'-diacetoxybenzophenone described above was concentrated and the product obtained repeatedly crystallised from alcohol when pale yellow needles (0.2 g.) were obtained, m.p. $150-51^\circ$. It analysed for a diacetyl derivative. (Found : C, 67.98; H, 4.92. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.45; H, 4.70%). As the quantity was very small further work could not be done on this product.

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-diacetylbenzophenone : A mixture of the 5,5'-diacetyl derivative (1 g.), dimethyl sulphate (2 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) in dry acetone (20 ml.) was refluxed for 16 hr. The product obtained on working up as usual was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $125-26^\circ$. (Found : C, 70.18; H, 5.6. $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 69.93; H, 5.56%).